

Looking for Spanish heathers

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At the annual conference at Falmouth in August 2012 Dr Jaimé Fagúndez, a member of The Heather Society and botanist from the University of A Coruña, gave a short presentation on a possible excursion he would like to organize for THS members to his part of Spain, Galicia, to see the local heathers in the wild. Eventually eleven members and three of their family and friends assembled in the wonderful old city of Santiago de Compostela for the four-day excursion. The group had quite an international flavour with Ella May Wulff and Dee Daneri from USA, Eileen Petterssen from Norway, Kurt Kramer and Dr Mike Pirie from Germany, Susie and Alan Kay from Ireland, Richard Canovan and Barry Sellers from England and myself from South Africa. Most of us knew each other from various Heather Society and North American Heather Society events stretching back over 20 years. Some of us had to arrive a day earlier because the flights from Gatwick were only on alternate days and Mike arrived on the second day because of university commitments in Mainz.

Galicia is very hilly with few large, open, flat areas, rather like the northern border country in Britain, and has a cooler, wetter climate than the rest of Spain. Our first day out from our charming hotel, Virxe da Cerca (not easily pronounced by us) was to two localities not far from Santiago. Pico Sacro, southeast of the city, is a small, isolated peak sticking out of pine and eucalypt plantations but the summit is a protected area, mostly free of alien plants. It is part of a quartzitic “island” that lower down is heavily quarried. Here we walked and clambered around and were able to see six heathers – *Erica arborea*, *E. cinerea*, *E. umbellata*, *E. australis*, *Calluna vulgaris* and *Daboecia cantabrica*. I was pleased to find a single white-flowered *Daboecia* growing in a larger shrublet of the pink variant. *E. arborea* was perhaps the commonest species – sadly with flowers well over. It was mostly short, up to 1.5m, with a few in sheltered areas on the cooler north-facing slopes to 2m. It was amazing to see small plants growing out of crevices on the rock-faces. The few plants of *E. umbellata* surprised me being only 0.25m tall when I was somehow expecting them to be up to 1m. They had a few flowers still out.

The second locality was totally different being a small flat wetland area west of the city near the Fervenza Reservoir at Zas. Here we were all in for a shock

Figure 1. A captive audience in a stand of *Erica tetralix* listening to Dr Jaimé Fagúndez's comments about the heaths in the Zas wetland: (left to right) Richard Canovan (photographing), Kurt Kramer, Gerd Wilkens, Alan Kay, Ella May Wulff and her cousin Alison Stein, Dee Daneri, Susie Kay, Barry Sellers and Eileen Petterssen.

having to walk single-file in a follow- my-leader style, the leader being myself having to bushwhack through impressive solid stands of *Erica tetralix* up to 1.5m tall. I wished I had an African panga to make progress easier. Jaimé was busy explaining things to the line behind me (Figure 1). I am accustomed to the low plants of *E. tetralix* on the Roundstone Bog in Connemara. In more open areas at Zas, where *E. tetralix* was not so dominant, patches of *E. ciliaris* occurred. In other areas taller woody shrubs, up 1.5m, of *E. erigena* grew in clumps. They were, of course, well over. Talk soon cropped up of hybrids and pollinators since there was no sign of any hybrids here, the classic *E. tetralix* × *E. ciliaris* cross producing *E. × watsonii* – why none here with many flowering individuals of both potential parent species being present (McClintock 1983)? At another part of the wetland the vegetation was much shorter and one could easily amble around in low stands of *E. cinerea*, *E. ciliaris*, *Calluna* and *Daboecia*, but no *E. tetralix* nor *E. erigena*, perhaps not sufficiently boggy?

After that we drove back to Negreira and indulged in a sumptuous luncheon that stretched over several hours! Then followed the long drive up north to the city of Ferrol, allowing us time to relax and digest our enormous lunch. This city was a thriving ship-building port and naval base but sadly the declining

economies in Europe have forced many closures including much of the naval base, so things were rather rundown. Two nights were spent here, with dinner in a restaurant-pub named Lar de Toxos, which soon got referred to as the “toxic one” for want of better pronunciation on our part, not that we experienced any problems with all the good food and wine.

Figure 2. *Erica mackayana* at Serra da Capelada.

Next day, off we drove to the northernmost part of Galicia and indeed Spain, through rugged hilly countryside, past occasional pink smatterings of *Erica cinerea*, to Serra de Capelada, a nature area. Here, high in the hills we entered natural pine forest with local wild horses that were inquisitive about our presence in their domain. Out, and scouting around, we soon had our first exciting sighting of fully

flowering *Erica mackayana* despite it not being wet and soggy (Figure 2). We had to follow the paths and openings created by the horses through the dominant gorse (*Ulex europaeus*) bushes. What a pest gorse is for browsing naturalists. There were also plants of *E. cinerea*, *E. vagans* and *E. erigena*, *Calluna* and *Daboecia*. In some instances, the heathers grew up in the gorse to a height of 1.5m: again a surprise for me who has only encountered some of them on Roundstone Bog. Then on to the highest point on a headland, San Andres de Teixido, high above the sea and fairly windswept. Here there was very low *E. cinerea* neatly pruned by the wind.

Another fine lunch stopover was made in the hills at a lovely farm restaurant with a nice view. This provided us with a guessing game thanks to Kurt Kramer who nosed around the lower part of the garden and noted a small shelter built with some dried heath branches. Some of us came to the conclusion it was most likely *Erica scoparia* imported from some populations in nearby northern Spain (see Nelson 2012).

After the delicious, extended lunch, we drove back south to Ferrol but not before Jaime said he would show us some lovely heaths in an unusual locality

Figure 3. Punta Frouxeira sand dune community, fine *Erica vagans* protected in its den.

– the coastal sand dunes near the lighthouse at Punta Frouxeira. Here we were treated to some fine, fully flowering shrublets of *Erica vagans*. I was very frustrated for my photography because the nicest heather plants were out of reach, well protected in a veritable sea of low, tightly packed gorse plus a thistle or two and some long bramble branches (Figure 3). There was no way that I could get to them without armoured spats! In the open short heath there were fine plants of *Calluna* and *E. cinerea*.

From our Hotel El Suizo in central Ferrol we went off to Monte Caxado where there was a veritable “woodland” of wind turbines stretching miles across the hill tops. The visit here was to see the effect of vegetation management by mowing or clearing of all taller shrubs, and to compare this with, nearby, the low, open pine woodland with its understorey of heaths and gorse. There were small, neat, flowering plants of *Erica cinerea*, *E. mackayana* and *Calluna* and some *E. umbellata* with a few flowers. This vegetation was controlled by the local horses, a very important factor in heathland conservation, said Jaime (Figure 4). Glad to get away from the cold, windswept hilltops we went down to the Natural Park Fragas del Eume and had a good walk along a paved road alongside a strongly flowing river through beautiful forests of oak and laurel

Figure 4. Barazon area. Slope with flowering *Erica cinerea* and a few *Daboecia cantabrica* and *E. umbellata* intermingled, and with taller *E. scoparia* and behind the advancing pine trees.

with the occasional tall *E. arborea* and, surprisingly, *Daboecia* growing out of rock-faces. For once it was a pleasure to see forest without hordes of alien eucalypts, but they were coming in! A pleasant lunch was had at the attractive, restored, ancient monastery near the head of the valley.

On Sunday, the last day of the trip, we drove east of Santiago through the old town of Melide where a mediaeval fair was being held and many pilgrims were walking through on their own personal “el camino”. We went out to a flat area where a business park was being set up and opposite which was a natural area, very boggy in places and full of lovely heaths but not easy to access without getting soggy shoes. The area was dominated by low *Erica scoparia* (not flowering) and *E. cinerea*, *E. vagans* and *Daboecia* and a few *E. umbellata* still with some flowers. One area had badly disturbed vegetation where *E. scoparia* was being bulldozed out. Among the mangled plants I managed to find an excellent example with its impressive lignotuber still attached (Figure 5).

En route back to Melide we passed some recently burnt areas and I got the bus to stop so that we could view the good examples of *Erica scoparia* shrubs

Figures 5 & 6. Melide area. *Erica scoparia* showing the lignotuber, and (right) resprouting vigorously after a recent fire.

vigorously re-sprouting with black, burnt stems still present (Figure 6).

After an enjoyable picnic lunch alongside a stream, we stopped outside a nearby cluster of farms and disturbed the Sunday siesta of the whole lot by walking through and rousing all the dogs, and went to a slope covered with indigenous vegetation and some scattered alien trees marching in from the surrounds. The dominant species was *Erica scoparia* with scattered patches of flowering *E. cinerea* and *Daboecia* and some *E. umbellata*. Jaimé also showed us several other plants that were local endemics.

Back at Hotel Virxe da Cerce we all got together and Jaimé, Mike and I gave members a talk on the latest research on the genus *Erica* and the way forward with our phylogeny work (see pp 35–41 this issue). Mike had brought a printout of the latest molecular tree to bowl over the members – it stretched along the table for 2.5 metres! That evening we held our final dinner in the old part of the city and were joined by Dr Ana Mugrabi de Kuppler and her young family. She completed her PhD at Bonn in 2013 on molecular phylogeny of mainly the European species of *Erica*. Several papers are being prepared for publication.

Thus ended for a knowledgeable and interested group of Heather Society members an excellent trip and set of excursions to see the heaths and heathers of Galicia under the able and friendly guidance of Jaimé Fagúndez. He, alas, has to move into heathland conservation now because funding for systematic research is no longer available to him, or very difficult to come by, due to the

economic crisis, but he will, fortunately, keep up his interest in systematics together with Mike and myself.

But, this was not the end of Spanish heaths for me. I left the next day by fast train for the 1,100km, day-long journey south to Cadiz in the southwest of Spain. I could have flown there but did not want to sit in airports and planes but rather look out of the train window at the passing scene. And this I certainly enjoyed. I was really surprised how few farms and villages there were as we rushed down around Portugal to Madrid. I could see lovely hills, mountains (some still with a bit of snowy topping), deep valleys with many reservoirs and alongside the railway line what looked like lots of heaths, probably non-flowering *Erica scoparia*, *E. australis* or *E. arborea* with the occasional flowering plants of *E. cinerea*. Much of this area I later noted on maps was allocated to natural parks (reserves).

In Puerto Real on the mainland opposite Cadiz I was met by my friend, Professor Fernando Ojeda, of the University of Cadiz who had invited me to stay with his family and wanted to show me the Andalusian heaths he knew from his ecological studies while studying in Seville. After his PhD he had come out to the Cape to see the many *Erica* species there and I had met him – that was way back in the late 1990s. He still comes out regularly to work on ecological aspects of our heaths, especially to try to understand the fascinating occurrence of seeding and re-sprouting after a fire in the colour variants of the single species *Erica coccinea*.

We went for some lovely drives and hikes in the mountains above Algeciras where we saw good cork-oak woodland being harvested for the bark and *Erica arborea* re-sprouting in the clearings. The heaths we observed were mainly *E. scoparia* with patches of *Calluna* and near a water-drip below cliffs *E. ciliaris* and *E. erigena*. Higher up there were some plants of *E. umbellata*. In the valley of Rio de la Miel there was lots of open heathland over the mountain slopes consisting mainly of *E. scoparia* and *E. australis*, both of which were re-sprouting in burnt areas or areas manually cleared for fire breaks. Fernando told me that *E. australis* cannot cope with too much slashing-and-burning and eventually dies out whereas *E. scoparia* survives this treatment. Again in a wet seep there was some *E. ciliaris* alongside the hiking path. In the forest going down into the gorge we passed through stands of cork and holm oaks with here and there in openings *E. arborea* up to 6m tall and a few *E. australis* and even some *Calluna* to 50cm. One spectacular area we visited were the white limestone mountains of the Sierra de Grazalema in a natural park where there are superb hiking paths

Figures 7 & 8. *Erica andevalensis* and (right) excavated rootstock.

with one slope covered with a forest of the striking, local, endemic fir, *Abies pinsapo*. Twisty roads and several small villages with red-tiled, white houses and narrow streets plastered against the slopes made the area so enticing to explore.

On a typically hot, sunny day we visited Seville for Fernando to show me his home town and for my interest in cathedrals. We then drove out west to the Portuguese border where we went to the hills near Huelva around the open mining areas of the Rio Tinto at Minas de Nerva, that classic “poisoned area” dominated by *Erica andevalensis* (Figure 7) with, surprisingly, small patches of *E. australis*. *E. andevalensis* was in full flower and an exciting sight to behold (McClintock 1983). It was clear that both species had woody rootstocks and were multi-stemmed re-sprouters (Figure 8).

The final day above Algeciras was clear despite the heat so we could see the Rock of Gibraltar and only 14km across the Straits was Africa. I was able to wave and shout that I would be back at the southern tip within a few weeks after a most thrilling excursion to see for the first time the heathers of Spain and their habitats in two dissimilar regions with two authorities as my guides.

References

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